

INTERNATIONALIZATION OF BUSINESS SERVICES THROUGH SHARED SERVICE CENTERS

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Abstract. *The article concludes that professional business services are a promising area for the internationalization of a country and its inclusion in global value chains, especially in the conditions of digitalization, lack of resources and availability of human capital of high quality. Shared service centers (SSC) are identified as a subject of international trade. The types of professional business services that are concentrated in the centers are defined, as well as the current trends and the advantages of SSC location in the countries under study are identified.*

Keywords: *professional business services, intellectual and process services, internationalization of services, a shared service center, international trade in services.*

UMUMIY XIZMAT KO'RSATISH MARKAZLARI ORQALI BIZNES XIZMATLARINI XALQAROLASHTIRISH

Xulosa. *Maqolada professional biznes xizmatlari mamlakatni baynalmilallashtirish va uni global qiymat zanjirlariga kiritish uchun, ayniqsa, raqamlashtirish, resurslarning etishmasligi va yuqori sifatli inson kapitalining mavjudligi sharoitida istiqbolli yo'nalish ekanligi haqida xulosa qilinadi. Xalqaro savdoning predmeti sifatida umumiy xizmat ko'rsatish markazlari aniqlanadi, markazlarda to'plangan professional tadbirkorlik xizmatlari turlari aniqlanadi, markazlar rivojlanishining hozirgi tendentsiyalari va ularning o'rganilayotgan mamlakatlarda joylashuvining afzalliklari aniqlanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Professional biznes xizmatlari, bilim va jarayonlar xizmatlari, xizmatlarni xalqarolashtirish, umumiy xizmat ko'rsatish markazi, xizmatlarning xalqaro savdosi.*

ИНТЕРНАЦИОНАЛИЗАЦИЯ ДЕЛОВЫХ УСЛУГ ЧЕРЕЗ ОБЩИЕ ЦЕНТРЫ ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье делается вывод, что профессиональные деловые услуги являются перспективным направлением для интернационализации страны и ее включения в глобальные цепочки добавленной стоимости, особенно в условиях цифровизации, недостатка ресурсов и наличия человеческого капитала высокого качества. В качестве субъекта международной торговли выделены общие центры обслуживания, определены виды профессиональных деловых услуг, которые концентрируются в центрах, выявлены актуальные тенденции развития центров и преимущества их расположения в исследуемых странах.*

Ключевые слова: *Профессиональные деловые услуги, интеллектуальные и процессные услуги, интернационализация услуг, общий центр обслуживания, международная торговля услугами.*

The increasing digitalization and automation of business processes, as well as the unification of international business practices, is contributing to the expansion of traded business services in the global economy, increasing their direct and indirect internationalization, as well as the concentration of these services in shared service centers, either outside the parent company's home territory or established for independent operations.

Digital transformation and its impact on internationalization have been studied by C. Rando, A. Hervé, R. Ventrup, and C. Brausers. Issues related to the import of capital and attraction of FDI for the production of business services were the subject of research by S. Suez, E. Van der Marve, T. Wisaak. Researchers G. V. Turban, E. D. Frolova, M. Y. Shishmintsev devoted their works to internationalization in the service economy, strategies for foreign trade, internationalization of small and medium-sized service providers. International organizations and large consulting companies annually analyze the state and dynamics of shared service centers. Nevertheless, unstable political and economic situation, sanctions pressure and corporate reshoring policy bring out the necessity to generalize knowledge about the actors involved in the internationalization of business services in the world economy. The said earlier determined the purpose of the study. Insufficient study of the stated problems, the significance of trade in business services for the diversification of the export basket and the ultimate positive effect on the population well-being underlined the relevance of the selected issue under study.

The basic methods of general scientific knowledge are used, expert opinions and international databases are analyzed. The use of these methods, as well as the methods of statistical analysis, groupings and expert assessments, will ensure the objectivity of the results obtained.

The increasing degree of internationalization of business services is associated with the development of information and communication technologies (ICT). If earlier the production and consumption of the studied service was mainly confined in one territory, today up to 20 % of the total volume of services rendered is characterized by direct internationalization (export), and more than 15% of these services remain unaccounted for in the balance of trade, as they are used in intermediate consumption and supplied to the foreign market as part of goods.

Changes in the nature of the services under study allowed to classify them with the definition of new criteria and to determine the directions of their development. The classification of business services into process and intellectual services, presented below, is a useful tool to identify the possibility of their replication and centralization in Shared Service Centers (also called "captive offshoring") or "Global Service Centers", a unit with greater autonomy. The latter term has gained popularity due to the geographical decentralization and fragmentation of business services value chains around the world. The process of establishing SSCs by foreign companies in the territory of recipient countries is, in fact, intra-directional internationalization.

Despite the existing differences between process and intellectual business services listed in the table, there is an "equalization" of value added in SSCs for the two types of services as a result of the influence of the trends. For example, for process services, which require labor resources of average qualification and knowledgeability level, customization (individualization of the service to meet the needs of the client), automation and complexity (different types of services under the "one-stop-shop" system), which increases their added value; intellectual services are subject to standardization (a component in services for replicability), commoditization (reduction of added value due to mass replicability), automation, which leads to a decrease in their added value.

Table 1 — Classification of professional business services in SSCs

	Intellectual Services	Process Services
Degree of Knowledge intensity	Unique non-repeatable operations with a high level of specialized knowledge to perform them (index from 0.33 to 1,23 [3])	Routine, repetitive operations with low level of specialized knowledge to perform them (index from -0,69 to 0.05 [3])
Economies of scale	Low feasibility; working in a small team; economies of scale are achieved by integrating artificial intelligence (AI)	High feasibility; due to the number of operations performed per unit of time; large staff or fully automatic data processing system
Production capacities, infrastructure and human resources in the location	High standards for the resources	Low standards, economies of scale are achieved
Potential for automation	Medium and low (e.g., the AI analyzes a candidate's resume and social media, gives a sample to a recruiter)	High (e.g. use of chatbots without subsequent interaction with a specialist)
Examples	Human Resources Policy Management; Software Development; Financial analytics and risk management; Integrated marketing communications; Legal Support; Consultations on tax optimization; R&D	Customer support services (billing, etc.); Contact Center, including AI; Hiring-related paperwork; Accounting; Software System Administration; Supply Chain management

Note - Source: [2].

Concentration of international trade in business services takes place in SSCs: up to 70 % of the volume of professional business services in the world are provided by SSCs and only 30 % by independent third-party suppliers [1]. The creation of SSCs is aimed at optimizing the activities of the parent company or increasing its efficiency.

The choice of location for SSCs depends on corporate policy and the type of business service: for example, intellectual services are often moved outside the company's headquarters to Central and Eastern European countries closed to the head office, with developed ICT infrastructure and high wages; while the services for supporting business processes are moved to developing countries in Latin America, Central and Southeast Asia with excessive low-wage labor resources. Companies now focus not only on economic efficiency, but also on technological advances, such as generative AI, and on a country's ability to implement a flexible human resources policy known as "Talent Regeneration", which implies changes in the education system,

structural elements in the labor market, as well as in immigration policy, government support and digital infrastructure.

To assess the attractiveness of countries for SSCs location, the Global Services Location Index was created, according to which India, China and Malaysia rank the first positions; Belarus is not represented; Russia dropped 15 points in 2023 to 36th position; Uzbekistan was ranked 40th for the first time in 2023 out of 76. In the decision-making process, companies also take into account the proximity of the head office to the SSC (flight connections, visa policy with regard to foreign citizens), more attractive conditions in the labor market compared to neighboring countries and in the office real estate market.

Along with the above-mentioned factors characteristic of the investment recipient country, external factors that are in constant dynamics are considered. Thus, Russia used to be the center of attraction of foreign companies' SSCs, which served the companies in the Russian-speaking region. As a result of the withdrawal of more than 400 Western companies, it became possible to attract their SSCs to countries that have a similar language and cultural environment, have a full access to foreign software and favorable conditions for the relocation of specialists. In view of the above, the increase in exports of services, including business services, was recorded in a number of neighboring countries in 2023: in Armenia by 47,6 %, in Kazakhstan by 33,5 %, in Kyrgyzstan by 87,2 %, Uzbekistan by 54 %. The growth rate of international trade in services in SSCs in 2023 amounted to 16 %, with a feasible growth rate of 19 % in 2 coming years. These factors should be taken into account in the development of socio-economic measures to encourage intra-directional internationalization of the professional business services.

In general, the growth of SSCs is associated with digitalization: the emergence of AI and Big Data, which help improve decision-making; "mobility" of services or control through remote devices connected to corporate networks; cloud computing and "platformization", providing constant access to services without regard to the geography of the provider (exceptions are countries with mandatory data localization and restrictions on cross-border flows of financial information).

Internationalization of business services through SSCs can be direct (export of services) or indirect (providing services to local exporting companies). For example, the Information and Technology Service Company SSC founded by SIBUR and Gazprom-Neft provides business services to other companies (B2B segment); TNK-BP's Regional Technical Center provides telephony, Internet access and cellular services to individuals (B2C segment).

When selecting the processes that are transferred to the SSC, companies are guided by the frequency of operations, their labor intensity, the possibility of unification and round-the-clock service. Business procurement services account for up to 84,27 % (P2P - Procure-to-Pay); sales management services amount to 76,4 % (O2C - Order-to-Cash); accounting services — 80,90 % (R2R - Record-to-Report); personnel management — 48,31 % (H2R - Hire-to-Retire); IT and business analytics — 41,57 % of the total volume of services provided [5].

The advantage of SSCs for the internationalization of business services is that SSCs are founded by large companies that possess the necessary competencies according to the world's leading practices. SSCs can be an infrastructural element of the Talent Regeneration system. As a result of knowledge transfer to independent suppliers among small businesses and local players, the quality of human capital and labor productivity improve and wages increase not only in the

company, but also in the sector as a whole. Thus, as a result of the emergence of SSCs in the Philippines in the early 2000s, the average salary in the sector increased by 15-20 % [4].

The analysis of professional and scientific literature allowed us to identify the following trends of SSCs. Most companies locate near the head office or the target market (reshoring, insourcing) those SSCs that directly interact with the client (front-office services), and in distant countries so as to perform business services for the company's auxiliary operations (back-office services). Remote working of employees is expanding and hiring is becoming global: for example, in the UK in 2020, up to 65 % of the sector's professionals work remotely. The reorganization of value chains continues with the closure of centers in South-East Asia and staff reductions. Here process services with a high degree of automation remain: customer support services, document management, recruitment, procurement and other services related to trade and system administration. SSCs in developed countries provide intellectual services with higher added value.

Thus, the article concludes that professional business services become a promising area for the internationalization of a country and its inclusion in global value chains, especially in the context of digitalization, lack of resources and availability of high-quality human capital. Shared service centers are identified as main providers of international trade in business services. The types of professional business services that are concentrated in SSCs are defined, the current trends in SSCs development and the advantages of their location in the countries under study are identified.

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